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TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH INNOVATIVE METHODS

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Annotation: *this article explores how to use the interactive methods as well as the role of modern methods in teaching military terms and using them with examples during the lessons.*

Key words: *interactive methods, graphic organizers, interactive strategies, military terms.*

Nowadays, a number of works are carried out in higher military educational institutions with the aim of training mature officers with deep knowledge, modern thinking. Cadets studying in military educational establishments are source of the most important goals for reading literature in foreign languages related to their profession, information on the internet, the formation of skills and abilities to be able to communicate, and have the ability to exchange ideas with foreign specialists.

At this point, we should note that even at the University of public safety, improved programs have been created for all stage cadets in English practical classes, according to which the use of non-traditional interactive methods that encourage cadets to think creatively and independently and its implementation into the course process is effectively carried out. As an example, we can mention a number of interactive techniques. At this point, we should note that even at the University of public safety, improved programs have been created for all stage cadets in English practical classes, according to which the use of non-traditional interactive methods that encourage cadets to think creatively and independently and its implementation into the course process is effectively carried out. As an example, we can mention a number of interactive techniques. GTM(grammar translation method), TPR(teaching physical response), CLT(communivative language teaching), Direct method, ADEPT(analogy, diagram, example, plain English, technical definition) method, Silent way, Audio-lingual, TBL(task-based learning), CBL(content based learning), PPP(presentation practice

product) and others. Within these, the CLT method is very effective, giving a good, self-expected result in the course of the lesson. Because when we implement this method in the course of the lesson, the teacher is not the learner controlled, it is obtained from real life, not pedagogical, of course, the learner will have a choice, not one, there will be more than one answer, and at the end thoughts will be concentrated. This method teaches cadets to think and communicate independently. The adept method also helps to briefly cover a broader topic. The CBL method, on the other hand, is particularly suitable for the military field, where it is worked with a map. [1]

While the implementation of these techniques in the course process is a little complicated, the effect will be positive if we can clearly and correctly direct it to the lesson. The creation of a language environment in knowledge lands of a non-philological orientation depends on the pedagogical skill of the teacher. Because in order to work with terms the teacher should devote hard work and time. Within the teaching methods, interactive methods are from methods suitable for the demand of modern pedagogy, which is divided into 3 groups.

- 1) graphic organizers
- 2) interactive strategies
- 3) interactive methods

Each of these is definitely used in a specific direction. While graphic organizers serve as a tool or educational method, strategies will require the teacher to take directions, and in an interactive method, someone will have to be evaluated. These include T-schema, BBB, Sinkwein, mental attack, and concept analysis, which are included in graphical organizers from within, are heavily used in the course of the lesson. In particular, the "analysis of concepts" method is of great help to cadets in the study of terms. For example, a number of military terms mentioned in the previous lesson are distributed by writing on one side of the table, while cadets write down the meaning of these words on the other side of the table.

Term	Meaning
battle	A major fight between armed forces during the course of a war
withdraw	If troops pull back they move away from contact with the enemy
dig in	To prepare a defensive position
advance	To move forward towards the enemy

In order to master the studied applied foreign languages, it is important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching, to implement new informative and pedagogical technologies. The use of textbooks, educational and methodological manuals, handouts and electronic materials in mastering the subject will activate the course process and arouse the interest of cadets in science. Modern methods of education in the teaching of this discipline: the use of electron post, foreign TV channels, the internet, which combines virtual authenticity, that is, work with electronic educational literature and a database, the targeted use of the internet gives great effect in the formation and development of knowledge and skills.

In the training of mature officer personnel, it is advisable to use interactive methods such as design, distance education, mental attack, group thinking, gallery, rotation, round table, Case study, Jigsaw, use of small group competitions, internet news and advanced pedagogical technologies.

Summing up from the above, it can be said that as a result of the large-scale work being done, the successes that we are achieving in education and in particular in the field of foreign language are manifested as significant effects of the “Uzbek model”, which we are giving in a short period of time. The most impartial assessment is an outlier. One such recognition is also proud of the fact that our country occupies the leading positions in the world in terms of the level of development of the educational system. This is the current expression of the consistent reforms carried out by the leadership of our state, the high emphasis on education.

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